

Determinant Employee Engagement and Career Development: Analysis of Transactional Leadership, Remuneration, and Organization Commitment

Wenny Desty Febrian^{1*}, Indra Sani²
Universitas Dian Nusantara, Jakarta, Indonesia
ITB Asia, Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Wenny Desty Febrian
wenny.desty.febrian@undira.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

A summary of the findings from earlier investigations will be provided, and researchers will draw some conclusions. The research method is a literature review derived from research articles related to the variable in various world magazines. The purpose of this study is to identify factors that drive employee engagement, mediating variables that may directly or indirectly affect employee engagement, and what is thought to drive employee engagement in organizations. It discerns the connection between two different variables. The title's previous article was relevant. There are some significant and non-significant variables, it turns out. The novelty of this study is that a new research model framework was formed, and the results of the literature review study showed the relationship between pay and employee engagement, and the results of the study showed that companies can create employee engagement. You can use the number of days as a reference.

INTRODUCTION

HRM success A good forethought can be a good place to start to smoothly implement the company's work program and achieve the organization's goals. To achieve the goals, it is considered important to increase human resources Company, because the key to success is profit Viable and successful company Personnel is an economic factor. The problem with this company is the lack of commitment from the company's HR department. Another problem arises with the company. The performance of each person in the company becomes important because you remember this company We make products. human resource needed to make the product Meets or at least exceeds quality standards The company stopped it. Most of the human resources of this company are employees whose performance affects the performance of the company, researchers find this study directly relevant and interesting. It was ready. The purpose of this survey is to find out the positive effects of increasing efficiency, commitment, and performance of staff on the subjects. In this section, the author should introduce the relevant research background, research problem, and research objective. In addition, the author can explain the research gaps addressed in this study. The Gallup organization classifies employees into three types based on the level of engagement. (1). Engaged employees are the builders of your organization. They are usually always the best at the tasks given to them. This type of employee is empowered and ready to use their full potential to work for the development of the organization. (2). This type of unmotivated employee focuses on tasks rather than achieving work goals. They perform tasks only according to their share and what the organization pays them. At work, I always wait for orders from my boss and I feel that there is a lack of manpower. (3). These types of workers who are actively laid off are informal workers. They openly express their frustration and dissatisfaction with their work. They also constantly resist and anticipate the downsides of future opportunities. In line with previous research, (Khtatbeh et al., 2020); (Acikgoz, 2019); (Morgeson et al., 2023); (Aman-Ullah et al., 2020); (Agustian Zen, 2023); (Jumawan & Widjaja, 2023).

The three elements are power, commitment, and acceptance. Through its physical and mental strength, Elan shows the commitment of its employees in productive work. Vitality is characterized by great strength Mental flexibility at work, optimal energy, courage, desire to give the best possible effort, willingness and desire to work seriously to achieve something Make the most of your assigned work Determination, never give up easily, keep moving . to bravely step forward to persevere in difficulties. Engagement is the employee's emotional attachment to their job. The mission describes the employee's enthusiasm for his work, and pride in the work done and the company. with a high engagement score clearly indicates working. Make it a valuable, exciting and challenging experience. you feel normal. He is passionate and proud of his work and organization. On the other hand, a low commitment score means something else. identify with works because they are not meaningful, inspiring or experientially challenging, sluggish, proud of their work and organization. Engagement is employee retention, which is explained by the behavior of

employees who give their full attention to their work. Absorption Describes the state of an employee in a good mood. He is absolutely crazy, very focused and serious about his work. when they are doing their work, time tends to pass so quickly that it is difficult for them to stop or leave work. In line with previous research (Hamann & Schiemann, 2021); (Susanto, Ali, et al., 2023); (Piasecki, 2021); (Piwowar-Sulej& Iqbal, 2023); (Hornyak et al., 2022); (Sawitri et al., 2019).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Employee engagement is an important strategy that companies must have in order to retain employees and actively develop them (Henokh Parmenas, 2022). A win-win situation for the organization and all employees is achieved through employee involvement and continual improvement. sun High employee engagement ensures optimal employee performance for your company. (AR, Muhammad Thamrin Saribanon et al., 2023). Employee engagement can be interpreted as an employee's bond with the company, emphasizing the employee's commitment to the company or positive employee attitudes and behaviors.(Susanto, Agusinta, et al., 2023) Employee engagement is about understanding the employee's role within the organization and having the energy and fighting spirit to align with the organization's goals and objectives. (Susanto, 2022). It also gives you a clear understanding of how your organization is achieving its goals, how change can serve you better, and the voice your employees must use to voice their ideas and opinions throughout their careers. Giving and deciding is also important. (Buda Prasada & Sawitri, 2019). Employee engagement as employee commitment and enthusiasm in their work and workplace. Such employee engagement helps organizations measure and manage employee perspectives on key elements of corporate culture. (Susanto & Sawitri, 2022). Many companies conduct performance research as a metric to measure employee engagement with the organization and analyze the relationship between employee engagement and key business outcomes. (Susanto, Parmenas, et al., 2023) The results of the survey can help you identify which engagement initiatives are achieving your desired goals (Zen et al., 2023). Surveys are very useful for measuring employee engagement, but companies also need to realize that employee surveys are different than other employee surveys. (Bersin, 2013). Employee engagement is important for companies. If a company has the best employees and is responsive to company needs, the company should strive to increase employee commitment to the company in order to increase employee retention. (Jumawan, 2023). Employee engagement is important for companies (Febrian & Rajab, 2023). If a company has the best employees and is responsive to company needs, the company should strive to Increase employee commitment to the company in order to increase employee retention (Rettrisunz et al., 2023)

The career development program is one of the company's support tools to encourage and motivate employees to develop according to better status and income) (Jumawan & Widjaja, 2023). No employee wants a stagnant career. They want progress to succeed. For him, career development is one of the company's priorities to offer employees opportunities to discover their

potential (Muhammad & Tahir, 2023). A structured career development program increases employee motivation, work productivity and job satisfaction. It drives employee performance and contribution. Ultimately, this program will affect the progress of more advanced companies (Rustiawan et al., 2023). In addition to hiring employees who have the potential to contribute significantly to the company, HR must carefully plan and organize careers. The results must be consistent with the desired goals of the company and employees. These career development jobs are a form of HR management implemented through a career development program (Wahdiniawati & Sarinastiti, 2023). Career development is one of the functions of human resource management, the support and relationship between the employee and the company (Sani Supriyanto et al., 2021). Although everything depends on the skills and commitment of employees, the company should provide a platform and support through a well-organized career development program. (Rony et al., 2021). The better the company's career development system, the easier it is for employees to develop their careers and the easier it is to influence the company's development. (Aima et al., 2017).

Compensation is another form of remuneration received by employees or managers of a company for their work. This usually includes base salary or wages, bonuses and commissions, but may exclude tips and reimbursements (Jałocha et al., 2014). The purpose of compensation is to maintain productive personnel within the company. From a company's point of view, proper remuneration prevents personnel "piracy" by third parties. Compensation is also expected to discourage staff from engaging in KKN practices as their income is maintained (Morrell & Abston, 2018). A goal that should not be neglected is to improve the well-being of people working in the company. Workers are therefore comfortable and calm while performing their duties. Companies should also provide reasonable compensation to their employees as compensation (Permata Sari & lima Krisna, 2021). A good company will certainly provide reasonable compensation for its employees. The company rewards its employees for improving their performance and achieving the organization's vision and mission. Rewards are also provided to attract competent and experienced employees and motivate them to perform effective and quality work. Essentially, effective reward involves the principle of personal fairness (Allen et al., 2004). In other words, what employees receive should match what they give to the organization. Then there is internal equity, which is the fairness between work weight and compensation received, and external fairness, which is the fairness of compensation received by employees within an organization compared to other organizations with equal rights. Fairness (Griswold & Rogers, 2020).

Transactional leadership is a leadership style in which a leader uses rewards and punishments to encourage obedience. This leadership style is also called leadership style (Tao et al., 2022). This management style assumes that people are not motivated to complete their tasks. Therefore, managers use rewards and punishments as tools to encourage obedience from subordinates in managing their organization. (Kalsoom et al., 2018). It also develops structure,

leadership and direction to motivate subordinates to complete tasks and get work done. Subordinates only do their work when they are paid. Therefore, officials must be paid to be ready to perform their duties. They also punish their subordinates so that they do not repeat their mistakes (Elenkov, 2002). Transactional management is a management style that uses disciplinary forces and various incentives to motivate employees to give their best. The term "transactional" refers to the fact that this type of leader motivates subordinates by exchanging rewards for achievements. This leadership style is based on setting clear goals for employees and using rewards and punishments to encourage performance (Kalsoom et al., 2018). Transactional leaders are people who lead through social interaction. For example, a new manager might say, "Trade one thing for another: jobs supported by rewards or vacation ticket giveaways. Event managers offer cash rewards for productivity or no rewards for lack of productivity. (Walumbwa et al., 2008).

An organization's management success depends primarily on its people management success. The level of engagement an employee has with their organization will determine the performance the organization seeks to achieve. In the world of work, employee engagement has a very important impact. In fact, some organizations deliberately include an element of engagement as one of the requirements for holding a position offered in a job posting. Each employee has different foundations and behaviors based on organizational commitments. Highly motivated employees have a strong desire to do their best and achieve organizational goals. Conversely, under coercive circumstances, unengaged employees perform suboptimal efforts.

Organizational commitment is the state in which an employee stands by a particular organization and its goals and aspirations to maintain membership in the organization (Lucy Wambui et al., 2017). The organization's commitment is One of the much-discussed behaviors within an organization, Examine as dependent, independent, or variable mediator. This is because your organization needs it. Employees with high commitment to the organization We can survive and continue to improve our services and products it generates (Rameshkumar, 2020). The commitment of this organization is a strong desire to maintain its status. Membership of a particular organization, a desire to strive accordingly with specific beliefs and acceptances as well as organizational desire, organizational values and goals (Creta & Gross, 2020). In short, attitude Reflect employee loyalty to the organization and processes A sustainable way for members of the organization to express themselves Concerns about organization and success and progress consistent (Claus, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The goal of writing this article is to review and summarize the literature review related to the implementation of employee engagement in multinational companies, so that readers will be aware of other career factors, transactions, management, recruitment, and organizational commitment that can be used to increase employee engagement through various methods. This study uses a literature review approach to achieve the research objectives. The mini-

assessment of employee engagement is conducted by reading and analyzing several peer-reviewed journal articles. A literature review, which compares various theories and earlier investigations, constitutes this research process. The following data gathering techniques are employed to get the information and data required for this work: Documents/Library, or a method of gathering data for document searches relevant to the research subject. The literature review analysis method combined with an inductive reasoning model is used for this study's data analysis. A data analysis method called content analysis is used to carry out the analysis procedure. In other words, a thorough explanation of the facts and circumstances, including their nature, traits, and substance, as well as the reasoning and application of inductive logic to reach conclusions.

RESULTS

Employee engagement is a method used by management to retain employees in a company. Companies that are already committed to their business usually go to great lengths to retain their employees. Based on the Employee Employment Act, we treat all employees equally regardless of their position, etc., and ensure commitment. Employee retention programs include excursions, training, and other programs that can increase employee retention within your organization. The main purpose of employee engagement is to create an atmosphere that allows employees to become more involved in the company. Additionally, another goal of employee engagement is to build strong relationships. This strong relationship makes every employee feel valued. They take pride in the office they work in and try to do what's best for the company.

If employee engagement is done well, companies will support more employees. The company also has employees who are always positive. Therefore, the company's main goals are easier to achieve. If your company is good at employee engagement, your company can connect with them. Having already engaged employees allows companies to attract loyal employees who are rarely absent for non-essential purposes. In addition, the company is always looking for employees who will uphold the company's reputation. Ways to increase employee engagement include creating a more supportive work environment that motivates future employees, offers a variety of positive suggestions, and considers the well-being of all employees. increase.

When conducting employee engagement, it's also a good idea to develop a strategy for developing employee engagement. This can be done by writing down the categories of employees in your company and then formulating a strategy that works for your company. To find out your level, company employees must complete a questionnaire called the Gallup Q12 Index. It provides 12 statements and gives employees the opportunity to demonstrate a scale from 1 to 5. 1 means completely opposite, 5 means strongly opposite. Agree. Employee engagement includes the following levels: very unconstrained, not engaged, mostly engaged, Involved, very devoted

DISCUSSION

According (Ketprapakorn & Kantabutra, 2022) Development is the personal improvement done by a person to execute career plan and the improvement by the human resources department to execute the work plan according to the roadmap or level of the organization. A corporate career describes all the position or positions that a person can undertake during their working life in an organization or in several organizations. From an employee's perspective, position is a very important thing because everyone wants a position that suits their desires and wants the highest possible position based on their abilities. Higher positions often lead to higher salaries, more responsibility, and better knowledge, which is what employees often expect (Ghani et al., 2022). So, as a person enters the world of work, they may wonder whether their career goals such as the top position they hope for are being achieved in the organization where they work. If someone finds that their career goals cannot be achieved within the organization, that person may not have high morale or motivation or even leave the organization (Karini, 2023). It must be emphasized that although human resources may play a role in these development activities, in reality, those most responsible are the workers involved, because they are the the ones that are of most interest and these are also the ones that I will harvest later and appreciate the results. This is one of the basic principles of career development. (Cherian & Jacob, 2013)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The purpose of this study is to locate literature that supports the academic study's variables and to offer findings for potential research gaps or other study subjects in the future. The study's recommendations can be utilized to extend your perspective in regard to the factors discussed in this article, particularly in the field of human resource management. Conceptual support for design proposals is provided by a literature search.

FURTHER STUDY

We hope that this study is just the beginning of human resource management and that other researchers will continue the recommendations provided because researchers are conscious of their limitations.

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